

Reviewers In online Media of the Decision To Restaurants in Thailand

Susaraporn Tangtenglam¹ Manasin Sonthanong²

^{1&2}(Faculty of Liberal Arts and Science Kasetsart University Kamphaeng Sean Campus,Thailand.)

ABSTRACT : This paper aimed to study 1) reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand With the quantitative method, the questionnaire covered 400 samples of tourist with non-probability and accidental sampling. Then, the data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the respondent's information and with the correlation and multiple regression to find out any concordances between the reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand. The research indicated that 1) for the whole of the bloggers, Product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.312$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to restaurants in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the restaurants in Thailand.

KEYWORDS - reviewers; online media; decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Current communication the message of Thai society is evolving rapidly. People can Contact can communicate all over the world by Connected via the Internet network makes the way. Lifestyle changes as well. Thailand is a country that uses social media widespread Allowing users to participate in the creation of things on the website Together and able to interact with the information that At Can be done on the website, and users can create content for exchange Spreading and distributing information both in the Individuals and groups of the poor have become like a sanctuary in the Internet or Also known as social media, it is a place for users to write. And describe the interests or actions that have been done and linked to the interests and activities of others. Including information about the garden, articles, pictures, works, meet, express opinions, exchange cribs Experience or common interests It is an enormous source of information that users can help create content based on individual or personal interests. [1]

Current service users the Internet is increasingly interested in finding information on the Internet in terms of news, entertainment, and the current population of Thailand. Of 67 million people each day, there is an average of 5 hours of active users per day, with most technology users on smartphones making up 24% and using them on average daily. Accounted for 3 hours per day in use, the usage level of the Social network Accounted for 25% of User in communication 3 hours per day in data communication usage per day and use it via social media Most Network Application accounted for 50% of users in the industry. Digital A Smart hand Phone accounted for 31% Users use smartphones to search for information, accounting for 95% Products, products and services accounted for 94% and Online trading accounts for 51% [2]

Which the Kasikorn Research Center Have forecasted value The market of the restaurant business in Thailand covers Usually the chain restaurants and restaurants around the batteries to be expected. The market value is in the range of 375,000 - 385,000 million baht, especially in Bangkok. Nowadays, the restaurant business has more options. According to the civilization of the city Online Role and communication Consumer and consumer messages tend to be more exposed to social media messages. The behavior is mainly used as the online communication channel in search. Restaurants to read reviews and make decisions about dining out online.[3] To communicate through social media Through social tools For use in communicating with each other Through your online channel connected to the Internet In which both the sender and the receiver must be involved with each other. [4]

For this reason, the entrepreneurs in the restaurant business. Necessary Yes Looking At A database must be created. For acquiring their own food through a chemical compounding strategy. Celestial A Online

Appropriate and understand the needs of The actuality of the customer page. A To meet the needs of eating Food out And each restaurant operator must try to focus on the Maintain customer base Because of the more intense competition Customers have more choices Customer resources For many searches Yes Raise Therefore entrepreneurs must Try to find a communication strategy through Social network That is a medium to reach the target consumers to get opinions Including reviews or gathering information about the real needs of the target audience as quickly and economically. [5]

As a result, to study reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand. To be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for hotel business operators and to build confidence in foreign tourists. This could enable economic recovery in the service industry to return to normal and rapid growth.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was tourist in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between June - December 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand. The content consisted of 3 parts as follows.

Part 1: General information of the respondents, namely gender, age.

Part 2: Information on factors used in the analysis of reviewers in online media

Part 3: Information on the concordance between the decision of results to the to restaurants in Thailand.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding general data of the respondents, the following were found:

For the general information of the respondents, it was found that 300 respondents, 80%, were female, and 100, 20%, were male. 187 respondents were between 31-40 years old, 43.50%. 137 of them were 30 - 20 years, 18.50%. There were 35 respondents aged 41-50 years, 17.50%, and were 28 respondents aged 51-60 years, 14%. For the age 61 and over, there were 13 respondents, 6.50%.

Factors for analysis of reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand

The results of the analysis of reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand as a whole were Product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.312$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to travel in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the travel in Thailand. by 62.5% ($R^2 = 0.625$) and the forecasting equations for the bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.312ZX_1 + 0.412ZX_4$

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results of the analysis of reviewers in online media of the decision to restaurants in Thailand as a whole were Product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.312$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to travel in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the travel in Thailand. by 62.5% ($R^2 = 0.625$) and the forecasting equations for the bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.312ZX_1 + 0.412ZX_4$ [6] Networking in social media as a free travel style Case study I Roam Alone found that the sample Who are interested in the contents of the substance that has been read will be shown Interest or not interested from clicking the Like (Like) button, press Share (Share) or commenting on the content. Have read (Comment) in addition, it is Inviting friends to discuss issues or content that they have read With people who have similar opinions without They must have known each other before. In addition, sharing or sharing Posting content or issues of interest also expands the online community, which creates a network. Independent travel online to be more efficient and sustainable. It also corresponds to [7] Beauty Marketing Blogger on social media "found that the content Using symbols to communicate Emotional or the use of video, images and music for communication in the content will result in More credibility to the content. [8] Do a study on Social media thought influencer communication strategies that influence group attitudes Followers found that a follower's social media usage showed media exposure behavior from Main personal interest Most of the time, content is more images and articles than video clips. This is because photos will create more attraction and interest. With blogger still This allows social media users or followers to feel close to that which they are connected to. This creates trust and Trust in bloggers As a result, bloggers have an influence on their decision to buy a product or service. [9] By promoting through the virtual image is valuable. The greatest influence on planning behavior in travel decisions was followed by public relations. Influential people in tourism And publicity through celebrities, respectively Popular reviews are often from influential reviewers on social media. Influencer is A group of people who like to write stories, stories, experiences that are The expertise was interesting. These people tend to have the ability to influence. Or make other people happen Trust and follow the idea until the following readers are interested in products and services and may lead to Buying decisions can be divided into two main groups: 1) Macro Influencer group is the group with the highest

100,000+ social media followers and 2) Micro Influencer groups are the top 5,000 - 100,000 followers, in conclusion, you can notice that the influencers will be able to reach a group of people. More than reviewers That the influencers will be able to reach a group of people. More than reviewers That is a regular tourist, but a regular tourist can give more credibility Influencer. [10]

III. CONCLUSION

The advancement of the technology A Computers and the Internet cause Social Giving Innovation is a social network widely known as "Social network" by this social network The at Public at Members are people of all genders and ages. Shea Nation and religion all levels of education, occupation and every sub-circle from the

All over the world are the messengers? Write content about Experience articles, photos and videos written by members. And made by yourself or found in other media and then shared with others who Are in their network via the Internet And social media Social networks are growing rapidly and steadily. Gave rise to the technological evolution of various types of social networks Make the present Social media To play a greater role in daily life It's not just for consumers. Some operators also use social media channels. It is a channel of communication with their customers. To inform make the present Social media To play a greater role in daily life It's not just for consumers. Some operators also use social media channels. It is a channel of communication with their customers. To inform including various marketing activities to encourage consumers to use the service, product or service including various marketing activities to encourage consumers to use the service, product or service.

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